

Stabilisation of Molybdenyl Cations with 4,4'-Dimethyl 2,2'-Bipyridyl in Different Salt and Non-electrolytic Complexes

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Manuscript received 16 October 1981, revised 14 April 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

The aqueous chemistry of molybdenyl cation MoO^{2+} has been studied. The heterocyclic base 4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl has been shown to function as diacidic base in strong hydrochloric acid medium to yield the salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$. The non-electrolytic complexes $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2]$ and $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}]$ have been isolated from the parent salt by hydrolytic and dehydrohalogenation reactions in solution and in solid state.

THE effect of substitution in 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl on the complexation of metal ions has been studied only in some isolated cases. It is known that 1,10-phenanthroline gives stable complex with iron, but, 2,9-dimethyl 1,10-phenanthroline fails to do this due to steric factor. Identical observations have been reported by the present author in the case of molybdenyl cation also. The similarity of MoO^{2+} with Fe^{3+} ion in high spin state has also been established¹.

In the present investigation the role of 4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl in the aqueous chemistry of molybdenyl cation has been fully investigated. The salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ and the non-electrolytic complexes $[\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}]$ (in two forms, reddish pink and green varieties) and $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2]$, isolated in pure state by the present authors, have been thoroughly studied by analytical and different physico-chemical methods. The interconversion of the products and reactants is shown below which establishes the stability of the "oxometal" entity MoO^{2+} in different chemical reactions.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade. Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically as molybdenum trioxide and chlorine was estimated as silver chloride². Nitrogen was estimated by Duma's method. The oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

4,4'-Dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridinium oxopentachloro molybdate(V), $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$: This anhydrous salt was prepared by reducing MoO_3 (2 g) with HI (2 ml) in hydrochloric acid (12 N) medium and the green crystalline salt was obtained by adding 2 g of the base, yield 5.3 g. (Found: Mo, 20.18; Cl, 37.68; N, 5.89. Calcd. for $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$; Mo, 20.20; Cl, 37.20; N, 5.88%). Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.9.

Oxotrichloro(4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl)molybdenum(V), $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ (reddish pink): Dehydrohalogenation was effected by refluxing 1 g of 4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridinium oxopentachloro molybdate(V) with 20 ml of dehydrated ethanol for about 1 hr under positive pressure of the solvent. The pink product was filtered, washed and dried in a vacuum desiccator, yield about 0.7 g. (Found: Mo, 23.49; Cl, 26.93; N, 7.47. Calcd. for $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$; Mo, 23.85; Cl 26.45; N, 6.95%). The oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.0.

Oxotrichloro(4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl)molybdenum(V), $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ (green): A sample of about 1 g of the parent salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_5]$ was refluxed with 15 ml acetonitrile for 3-4 hr. The evolved gas contained hydrogen chloride. The bright green crystalline solid so formed was filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator, yield about 0.65 g. (Found: Mo, 23.69; Cl, 27.14; N, 7.12. Calcd. for $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$; Mo, 23.85; Cl, 26.45; N, 6.95%). The oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.09.

Alternatively, the green compound can also be prepared by refluxing the parent salt with acetonitrile or heating the parent salt in solid state at 250° for 2 hr in CO_2 atmosphere.

Oxo- μ -dioxochloro(4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl)molybdenum(V), $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2]$: Hydrolysis of the parent salt (1 g) was effected by boiling with distilled water when the orange red solid separated. It was cooled, filtered in a sintered gooch crucible, washed with cold water and dried

in vacuum desiccator, yield 0.75 g. [Found: Mo, 27.44; Cl, 10.02; N, 8.04. Calcd. for $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2 \cdot (\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2$; Mo, 27.62; Cl, 10.21; N, 8.05%]. The oxidation state of the metal was found to be 5.04.

This compound is insoluble in water and common organic solvents. Boiling it with 6 *N* hydrochloric acid produces the reddish pink $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$.

Conductivity measurements: The extensive hydrolysis and ionisation of the oxopentahalomolybdate(V) ion was confirmed by conductance measurement of the salts in aqueous medium. The non-electrolytic nature of $\text{MoOX}_3 \cdot \text{L}$ type of compounds was established by conductance measurements in acetonitrile. The conductance values in $10^{-3} M$ solution, of the reddish pink and the green forms of $[\text{MoOX}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}]$ are 5.02 and 5.26 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$, respectively which are much less than those for binary electrolytes (the conductivity of a 1 : 1 electrolyte in $10^{-3} M$ solution ranges from 120-160 $\text{ohm}^{-1}\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$). Since the hydrolytic product $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2$ is practically insoluble in almost all solvents, conductance measurement was not possible.

Measurement of magnetic susceptibility: Magnetic susceptibility measurements of the compounds were carried out at room temperature using Gouy balance having a field strength of 8500 gauss and the values of effective moments were found using the formula $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 (\chi'_M \cdot T)^{1/2}$ where χ'_M is the molar susceptibility after diamagnetic correction. The μ_{eff} values of the compounds $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2 \cdot [\text{MoOCl}_3]$, $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ (reddish pink), $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ (green) and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2$ are 1.81, 1.81, 1.88 and 0.52 B.M., respectively.

It appears from the results of magnetic susceptibility measurements that the salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2 \cdot [\text{MoOCl}_3]$ and both varieties of the mononuclear complex $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ contain quinquevalent molybdenum having d^1 configuration. The hydrolytic product $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2$ has a small magnetic moment due to oxobridges with a possible Mo-Mo interaction.

Thermogravimetry: Thermogravimetric investigations were made in a T. G. Analyser of Ciecoco Pvt. Co. The results are plotted in Fig. 1. It appears that at 250° the stable state corresponds to the weight loss of 15.11%, whereas the theoretical weight loss according to the following thermal dehydrohalogenation is 15.35%. Therefore, the non-electrolytic paramagnetic derivative $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ can be prepared at this temperature.

At 570°, the total weight loss is 70.36% which is in excellent agreement with the formation of MoO_3 which requires a theoretical weight loss of 69.69%. The synthesis of $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$ by thermal

Fig. 1. TGA Diagram of $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2[\text{MoOCl}_3]$.

dehydrohalogenation of the salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2 \cdot [\text{MoOCl}_3]$ has been mentioned which also confirms the thermogravimetric analysis of the compound.

IR spectra: Infrared spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer IR spectrophotometer using KBr pellet. The ir spectrum of the salt $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2 \cdot [\text{MoOCl}_3]$ shows a strong absorption band at 980 cm^{-1} while for the two isomers it appears at 960 cm^{-1} (*cis*) and 965 cm^{-1} (*trans*), respectively. The hydrolysed product $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}_2(\text{Me}_2\text{bipy})_2$ shows strong absorption at 945 cm^{-1} . These bands can be assigned to the molybdenum oxygen stretching frequency, indicating the presence of Mo(V)=O species in all the compounds.

Examination of the stretching frequencies indicates that there is a gradual decrease in metal-oxygen bond strength from $\text{Me}_2\text{bipyH}_2 \cdot [\text{MoOCl}_3]$ to hydrolysed product, as the chlorine atom is replaced by a nitrogen atom (from 4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridyl) and an oxygen atom (forming an oxobridge) causing a reduction in the value of the stretching frequency. This is probably due to the strong donating capabilities of the nitrogen atoms of Me_2bipy and oxygen of oxobridge, causing increased electron density around the central metal atom and thereby reducing its π -acceptance capacity and ultimately the metal-oxygen bond strength. The broader bands in the region 700-800 cm^{-1} in the case of hydrolytic product may be assigned to metal oxygen chain ($-\text{Mo}-\text{O}-\text{Mo}-\text{O}$) vibrations.

UV and visible spectra: UV and visible spectra were recorded on a Hilger Uvispek spectrophotometer. The solvent used in the case of the salt was 10 *M* hydrochloric acid and in the case of both the isomeric varieties of $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$, it was acetonitrile (A.R.). As the hydrolytic product is insoluble in common organic solvents, its reflectance spectrum was taken in the solid state using spectrochemically pure liquid paraffin. Reflectance spectra were also taken for the two isomers of $\text{MoOCl}_3 \cdot \text{Me}_2\text{bipy}$. The absorption bands together

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF THE SALT AND NON-ELECTROLYTIC ISOMERS

Compound	λ_{max} m μ	ν (cm $^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-3}$)	Molar extinction coefficient ϵ	Assignment
Me ₂ bipyH ₂ [MoOCl ₅] in 10 M HCl	700	14.29	13.50	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	440	22.72	15.04	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	370	27.03	207.00	² B ₂ → ² E (II)
	295	33.90	15,450	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
	232	43.10	12,000	² B ₂ → ² E (III)
[MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy] (reddish pink) in acetonitrile	740	13.51	90.00	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	520	19.23	708.00	L → Mo Charge transfer
	430	23.25	504.00	² B ₂ → ² B ₂
[MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy] (green)	870	27.03	900.00	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
	750	13.33	65.00	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	530	19.23	125.00	L → Mo Charge transfer
	375	26.67	660.00	² B ₂ → ² B ₂
	305	32.78	10,900	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
240	41.67	15,800	² B ₂ → ² E (III)	

with molar extinction coefficient and the corresponding intensities in the case of reflectance spectra and their tentative assignments are given in Tables 1 and 2. The results clearly agree with previous observations^{4,5}.

TABLE 2—REFLECTANCE SPECTRA IN SOLID STATE

Compound	ν (cm $^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-3}$)	Intensities	Assignment
MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy (reddish pink)	13.50	s	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	19.60	sh	L → Mo Charge transfer
MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy (green)	22.90	m	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	26.80	sh	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
	14.00	m	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	18.90	w	L → Mo Charge transfer
Mo ₂ O ₇ .Cl ₂ (Me ₂ bipy) ₂	23.40	sh	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	26.00	m	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)
	11.50	m	² B ₂ → ² E (I)
	17.50	sh	L → Mo Charge transfer
	22.90	sb	² B ₂ → ² B ₁
	26.20	m	² B ₂ → ² B ₂ (I)

s=strong; m=medium; w=weak; sh=shoulder;
sb=strong broad.

Results and Discussion

The MoOCl₅²⁻ ion is visualised as a tetragonal structure with a short Mo—O bond having C_{4v} symmetry⁶. The expected transitions with identical scheme agree very closely with the experimental results. The salt 4,4'-dimethyl 2,2'-bipyridinium oxopentachloromolybdate(V) in 10 M HCl shows two crystal field transitions ²B₂→²E (I) and ²B₂→²B₁ at 14,290 and 22,720 cm $^{-1}$ and three charge transfer transitions ²B₂→²E (II), ²B₂→²B₂ (I) and ²B₂→²E (III) at 27,030, 33,900 and 43,100 cm $^{-1}$, respectively. About the monomeric complex [MoOCl₅.Me₂bipy], the molecular orbital picture

is expected to be different. In this case the number of symmetry elements is expected to be less than that in the case of MoOCl₅²⁻ ion which belongs to C_{4v} point group. But the other distortions from octahedral structure compared to the distortion caused by Mo—O interaction are expected to be moderate. There may be considerable π -interaction with the filled π -orbitals of the ligand and metal d-orbitals. Therefore, a red shift is logical consequence of this effect and this has actually happened in this case as the following ν -values of the first crystals field transition reveal.

Compound	ν in cm $^{-1}$ $\times 10^{-3}$
(a) Me ₂ bipyH ₂ [MoOCl ₅]	14.29
(b) [MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy] (reddish pink)	13.51
(c) [MoOCl ₅ .Me ₂ bipy] (green)	13.33

The solution and reflectance spectrum of the two isomeric forms of [MoOCl₅.Me₂bipy] are similar. A new band appears in the region 19,000 cm $^{-1}$ which may be due to a Me₂bipy→Mo charge transfer transition. In the case of Mo₂O₇.Cl₂(Me₂bipy)₂, the L→Mo charge transfer band has undergone a red shift compared to the mononuclear complex [MoOCl₅.Me₂bipy], as the chlorine atom has been replaced by oxygen (forming bridge) which is expected to reduced the Mo-ligand bond strength.

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